

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Atambo****FIRST NAME: Anne****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (Microsoft Word for Microsoft 365 MSO (Version 2409 Build 16.0.18025.20160) 64-bit)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text:

1. Academic essays (EUCLID 2024, 7-14)
2. Creative writing (EUCLID 2024, 9)
3. Standard British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34)
5. Principles of when not to cite (EUCLID 2024, 34-38)
6. Style guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-50)
7. Tips for effective writing (EUCLID 2024, 10-13)

ACADEMIC WRITING: CONSCIOUS UNLEARNING AS A MEANS TO LEARNING

1) INTRODUCTION

The common adage: “The journey of a thousand miles begins with one step”, is a rather poignant phrase that can be applied to describe the ultimate completion of any pursuit, academic, nonetheless. The phrase indicates the numerous cumulative steps that build up to form the whole. In my experience, however, the phrase has lent much less attestation to the immense struggle that often entails taking the first step toward any goal. Academic writing is no less different. A student is required to engage in a series of learnings and, by doing so, is gradually equipped to gain mastery of a subject matter by conquering incrementally demanding tasks. Whereas the finish line of such engagements is expectedly lauded with praise and glory, the path leading to this end requires endurance, learning and unlearning to realise success.

In this response paper, I shall present through an academic essay the learning and unlearning elements I encountered while reading the resources provided for the academic writing unit ACA-401/ACA-401D, period one, revised by Prof Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr Kabiru Gulma. At first glance, the course is presented in a surprisingly simple yet comprehensive approach that encourages readers to reflect as they read. However, this delivery provides a first lesson on the art of academic writing. In my case, the challenge posed was to edify my style, methods, and overall writing standards. These elements were positively challenged, and the principles of these aforementioned areas were effectively addressed in the assigned learning resources.

Academic essays contain elements of formality, citations or references to other works to provide evidence-based responses to a hypothesis under interrogation (EUCLID 2024, 7). The main points discussed in this academic essay represent elements that question initially held beliefs or previously accepted practices that I would have to unlearn as I start my doctoral studies. All elements presented shall identify points for which the initial departure requires conscious unlearning to embrace the key lessons prescribed by the course instructors. This entails concepts spanning creative writing, using Standard British English, plagiarism, principles of when not to cite, style guides, and tips for effective writing.

2) CONSCIOUS UNLEARNING

My expectation coming into the program offered by EUCLID University was to engage in a doctoral program that would focus on subject matter expertise. Upon conclusion of the assigned learning resources, it became evident that the stellar standard of excellence expected to deliver said expertise is one that all learners have no other option but to grasp. For this reason, the concepts call for deliberate unlearning and simultaneous relearning on my part. These concepts are also highlighted and elaborated upon in this essay, hoping these principles will serve as a firm foundation for the rest of my study.

a) Creative writing

Creative writing is an element that requires imagination. However, for academic writing to be effective, it must remain critical and analytical (EUCLID 2024, 9). A compelling writer and scholar must be comfortable interrogating ideas and notions that do not align with their objectives. This includes acknowledging criticisms and ideas that disprove the hypothesis of the writer. Ultimately, this lends service to problem-solving as it allows the learner to use writing to explore a broad range of perspectives about the topic under study and develop potential solutions through further research.

While I may have previously drafted long-drawn papers, reading resources provided by Dr. Kabiru has allowed me to appreciate the creative elements embedded in academic writing. It is a dance with words, ideas, theories, and justifications that should delicately lead to a solemn truth devoid of fanciful conclusions. Granted, I find the reading

materials provided for this module to be essential and a valuable resource as I begin my doctoral studies.

b) The use of standard British English

As a Kenyan National, memories of my upbringing are filled with exposure to British politics, current affairs, and, to an extent, British popular music championed by the ever-blasting British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) radio channel at my childhood home. On the other hand, standard American English (SAE) was also equally pervasive growing up courtesy of the influence of pop culture, entertainment, and the sociolect of the bulging urban youth populations (EUCLID 2024, 25). Having thus an affinity toward the indiscriminate use of standard American and British English (SBE) languages, I must pay particular focus on using words and phrases in spelling and meaning.

Regarding formal schooling, SBE took the crown. All applicable study forms were undertaken in English and were in line with SBE grammar rules. Due to this prolonged conformity, I shall adhere to SBE grammar rules, perhaps more strictly and consistently.

3) LEARNING NEW PRINCIPLES

While reading through the learning resources provided by Dr Kabiru, I realised that my desire to excel as a doctoral candidate became heightened. Excellence as an aspiration may not be an ideal objective to work towards. However, the pursuit of excellence, defined by progressive, cumulative steps, took centerstage when reading the assigned materials. Perhaps this attribute was ignited by how the instructions were communicated, namely, in simple and precise delivery. I hope that this prowess, among others, shall be a skill I master and employ for the good of knowledge and innovation.

a) Plagiarism

“Ignorance is no excuse” was the motto of my primary school in Nairobi, Kenya. I, therefore, read the plagiarism part of the reading materials with much intrigue. The essential truth regarding plagiarism is aptly summarised as: Give to Caesar what belongs to Caesar! And all should be well – you hope! By definition, plagiarism is using another’s words, works, or thoughts and passing them as your own (EUCLID 2024, 34). As I always plan to pay my dues, It shall, therefore, remain my goal to get acquainted with the appropriate citation standards to acknowledge the efforts and inputs of other scholars that influence, inform, or challenge my research and writing.

While plagiarism is universally shunned, the chances of falling victim to this misfortune abound. I plan to rely on the institution’s resources for ethical scholarship. This includes the ardent use of Grammarly and Turn-it-in.

b) Principles of when not to cite

While reading through the topic of plagiarism, I found myself amused at the topic of knowing when not to cite. In my formative years, I was bound to provide citations for many of my thoughts. It is relieving to receive the green light to rid myself of this burden of citing “enough.” As pointed out in the reading materials, using signal phrases, which entails employing verbs followed by an author's name (EUCLID 2024, 38), can provide an alternative remedy to a recovering overzealous citer such as myself.

c) Style guide

As I begin to find my voice through writing, I plan to develop a style of writing that will nobly serve my academic pursuits. For now, I am interested in developing the ability to interrogate topics, use abbreviations, master the presentation of an essay structure and, last but not least, get acquainted with the Chicago style, as published by the University of Chicago Press in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS). For the writing of research papers, I will rely on Turabian's *Manual for Writers*, which is the CMS official adaptation for use on final manuscripts such as research papers and dissertations (EUCLID 2024, 50).

d) Tips for effective writing

Writing is a skill that can be learned and developed. I plan to abide by tested rules to guide my writing experience, namely revising the draft materials, proofreading the writing, sticking to the topic under discussion and starting early (EUCLID 2024, 11). The demands of everyday life, work and scholarship may be at loggerheads at one point or another, but developing a routine may make it easier to tackle research and writing.

4) CONCLUSION

The challenge of pursuing doctoral studies requires commitment. The learning resources provided for this module presented sincere principles that learners must contend with in the journey toward academic engagement. I look forward to making the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack my writing companion for the months ahead. Ultimately, the thousand steps ahead will feel less and less insurmountable. Instead, this first writing assignment has proven to me that all I need to focus on is the process and key lessons, for as in due time, the outcome shall reveal itself once the proverbial journey of a thousand steps is concluded.

REFERENCES

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